

REACTIVE POWER COMPENSATION TECHNOLOGIES.**Tobvoyev Akram.**

*Candidate of Technical sciences of the Department "Electric Power Engineering"
Navoi State Mining and Technological University.*

Xudoyorov Shuhrat.

*Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, "Mathematics-Informatics" faculty, senior
teacher of the Department of Informatics.*

Raximova Shahrizoda.

*Student of the Department of Electric Power Navoi State Mining and
Technological University.*

Annotation. Reactive power compensation is the management of reactive power to improve the performance of an network. In general, the problem of reactive power compensation is related to load and voltage support. In addition to the goals, improving the power factor of the system to balance the real power from the mains, strengthening voltage regulation, and eliminating the harmonic components of large fluctuations in non-linear industrial loads. Voltage maintenance is generally required to reduce voltage fluctuations in a transmission power line. Reactive power compensation improves the stability of an system by increasing the maximum active power that can be transferred.

Key words: Longitudinal and transverse compensation, series compensation, equivalent resistance, reactive power, capacitors to reduce equivalent reactance.

Longitudinal reactive power compensation. Reactive power compensation can also be of another type. Typical transverse compensation systems use capacitors to reduce the equivalent reactance of the mains component at nominal frequency (fig.1). Thus, the capacitor C connected in series generates reactive power, which balances part of the reactance of the line. This is due to the resonance of the voltages in the capacitor and the inductance, directed oppositely (at an angle of 180°). An

arrester and a varistor are used to avoid the destruction of the capacitor C from overvoltages.

Picture 1. Longitudinal compensation with protection.

Traditionally fixed or mechanically switched capacitors or inductors or synchronous compensators are used for reactive power compensation. However, in the last few decades, two new families of reactive power generators using power electronics have emerged: static thyristor compensators and self-commutated static converters (Fig. 2).

This is equivalent to increasing the inductance, i.e. reduction of reactive power consumed by the reactor. The main disadvantage of this configuration is the generation of harmonics, which makes it necessary to implement a more complex topology (with passive filters, using a delta connection or a twelve-pulse configuration).

Picture 2. Thyristor-controlled reactors.

Thyristors are also used for series compensation. Thyristor-controlled series compensator is a technology that eliminates certain problems in dynamic power transmission systems (Fig.3). Thyristor-controlled series compensators are an excellent damping tool when connecting large electrical systems. In addition, they reduce subsynchronous resonance problems, a phenomenon that involves the interaction between large power units and the compensation of transmission systems.

Picture 3. Thyristor-controlled longitudinal compensator.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The advantages of such installations of longitudinal compensation include:

- symmetrical bus voltage;
- reduction of voltage fluctuations and increase of its level at electrical receivers.

Minuses:

- difficult operating conditions for the capacitors of the installation compared to transverse compensation, since the short-circuit current of the traction network flows through the capacitors, and reliable ultra-fast protection is needed here;
- overload of capacitors in dangerous modes: forced, emergency, post-emergency.

In order to achieve the best effect from reactive power compensation, adjustable installations with combined operation of longitudinal and transverse compensation should be used. [1,2]

The advantages of using longitudinal compensation systems in general include:

- increase in power transmitted over the line;
- increasing the stability of the operation of power systems at peak loads;
- significant reduction in active power losses;
- improving the quality of electricity in networks;
- high efficiency of power distribution in parallel lines;
- there is no need to build generating sources in remote areas;
- intersystem sections and technical parameters of lines do not need to be increased. [2,3]

Too high, or as it is also called, reactive energy and power, contribute to a significant deterioration in the operation of electrical networks and systems. We propose to consider in our article how automatic compensation of reactive power and overcompensation in networks at enterprises, in an apartment and at home is carried out. You need to understand that the more resources spent on production, the higher the price of the final product. If it is possible to reduce the cost of manufacturing a product, a manufacturer or entrepreneur will be able to reduce its price than to attract potential customers and consumers. [3,4]

In order for energy and reactive power to be compensated by capacitor banks and synchronous motors, an energy saving installation is required. Most often, such devices are used with a relay, although a contactor or thyristor can be installed instead. At home, relay arc compensation devices are used. But if reactive energy and power are compensated in factories, at transformers (where there is an asymmetric load), then it is much more expedient to use thyristor devices. But there is also an individual single-phase compensation of reactive energy and power (or transverse), its price is much lower. In this case, ordered control devices (capacitors) are installed directly at each power consumer. This is the optimal output if a three-

phase motor or electric drive is being controlled. But this type of compensation has a significant drawback - it is not regulated, and therefore it is also called unregulated or non-linear. [5,6]

III. CONCLUSION.

In order to increase the efficiency of existing power lines, as well as to improve their capacity, devices for longitudinal compensation of reactive power are used. Today, the abundance of various generating sources of various capacities, as well as high-voltage lines, especially those that transmit electricity over long distances, leads to an increasing demand for increasing not only the reliability of energy systems as a whole, but also for improving their efficiency. The main economic advantage of using longitudinal compensation devices is energy saving. Not only is power quality improved, but the number of transmission lines can also be reduced if series reactive power compensation is applied. Protecting the environment is a natural consequence of implementing this technology, especially on a large scale. Installation costs are such that a new transmission line costs 10 times more than a series compensation device with the same capacity. As a result, the payback of such a system is only a few years, compared with traditional transmission lines.

REFERENCES.

1. Ovchinnikov A. Losses of electricity in distribution networks 0.38 - 6 (10) kV - Electrical Engineering News, 2013
2. Zhelezko Yu.S. Principles of regulation of electricity losses in electrical networks and software for calculation. - Power plants, 2001, No. 1. 9, p. 33
3. Savina N.V., Myasoedov Yu.V. V. Systematic studies of power losses during the operation of distribution electrical networks // Bulletin of ISTU. 2012. No. 1 (60). pp. 142–148.
4. Siruk S.A., Kosharnaya Yu.V. V., Evgrafov S.A. and others. Influence of sub-subscriber load on the level of electricity losses in the networks of power supply organizations.// Industrial Energy. 2010. No. 8. pp. 9-15.

5. Tovboyev A.N., Ibodullayev M.I., Norqulov A.O. Uch fazali zanjirlarda subgarmonik ferrezonanslarning matematik model yordamida tahlili // Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya instituti “Fan va texnologiyalar taraqqiyoti” Ilmiy – texnikaviy jurnal 2021. №2 -s.155-160
6. Ibadullaev, M., Tovbaev, A.N. Research of Ferropesonance Oscillations at the Frequency of Subharmonics in Three-Phase Non-Linear Electric Circuits and Systems// Rudenko International Conference on Methodological Problems in Reliability Study of Large